

proline rich transmembrane protein 2 or infantile convulsions and paroxysmal choreoathetosis or Paroxysmal kinesigenic dyskinesia/choreoathetosis (PRRT2 / PKC) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : Mutations in PRRT2 lead to Paroxysmal kinesigenic dyskinesia (PKD) (also called paroxysmal kinesigenic choreoathetosis (PKC)) and Familial hemiplegic migraine (FHM). It has been implicated in benign familial infantile epilepsy, infantile paroxysmal torticollis, benign infantile epilepsy and Down syndrome, to name a few. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of PRRT2, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my

*ML dicoveries of PRRT2 synergy in Meningiomas

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limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: PRRT2, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

Contents

1 Introduction	2
1.1 Meningioma	2
1.1.1 World Health Organization (WHO) classification	2
1.1.2 Historical perspective	3
1.1.3 Pathophysiology	4
1.2 proline rich transmembrane protein 2 (PRRT2)	4
1.3 Roles of PRRT2 in different disease	5
1.4 Insight behind the work	6
1.5 Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution	6
2 Methods	7
2.1 Static data from Patel et al. [1]	7
2.2 Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]	7
2.3 Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R	8
2.4 Regarding biological insight	8
3 Results & Discussion	9
3.1 PRRT2 related synergies	9
3.1.1 PRRT2 - individual genes	9
4 Conclusion	12

1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there

exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossil, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. proline rich transmembrane protein 2 (PRRT2)

Paroxysmal kinesigenic dyskinesia (PKD) is the most common type of paroxysmal movement disorder and is often misdiagnosed clinically as epilepsy. Chen et al. [13] identified three truncating mutations within PRRT2 (NM_145239.2) in eight Han Chinese families with histories of paroxysmal kinesigenic dyskinesia, i.e. - • c.514_517delTCTG (p.Ser172Argfs*3) in 1 family, • c.649dupC (p.Arg217Profs*8) in 6 families and • c.972delA (p.Val325Serfs*12) in 1 family. They observed that these truncating mutations co-segregated exactly with the disease in these families and were not found in

1,000 control subjects of matched ancestry. PRRT2 is highly expressed in the developing nervous system, and a truncating mutation alters the subcellular localization of the PRRT2 protein. They proposed further investigation of function of PRRT2 and its role in paroxysmal kinesigenic dyskinesia.

PKD is a paroxysmal movement disorder characterized by recurrent, brief attacks of abnormal involuntary movements induced by sudden voluntary movements. Wang et al. [14] identified PRRT2 as a causative gene of PKD by using a combination of exome sequencing and linkage analysis. By combining the defined linkage region (16p12.1-q12.1) and the results of exome sequencing, they identified an insertion mutation c.649_650InsC (p.P217fsX7) in one family and a nonsense mutation c.487C>T (p.Q163X) in another family. Confirmation of findings followed, when the c.649_650InsC (p.P217fsX7) mutation was identified in two of these families, while a missense mutation, c.796C>T (R266W), was identified in another family with PKD. Thus, they identified PRRT2 as the first causative gene of PKD.

1.3. Roles of PRRT2 in different disease

Benign familial infantile epilepsy (BFIE) is a self-limited seizure disorder that occurs in infancy and has autosomal-dominant inheritance. Heron et al. [15] identified heterozygous mutations in PRRT2, in 14 of 17 families affected by BFIE, thus indicating that PRRT2 mutations were the most frequent cause of this disorder. They further reported PRRT2 mutations in 5 of 6 families affected by infantile convulsions and choreoathetosis (ICCA) syndrome (marked with infantile seizures and an adolescent-onset movement disorder, paroxysmal kinesigenic choreoathetosis (PKC) co-occurrence). These findings showed that mutations in PRRT2 caused epilepsy as well as a movement disorder. Furthermore, PRRT2 mutations elicited pleiotropy in terms of age of expression (infancy versus later childhood) as well as anatomical substrate (cortex versus basal ganglia).

Dale et al. [16] reported 4 family members with PRRT2 mutations who had heterogeneous paroxysmal disorders. They observed that the index patient had transient **infantile paroxysmal torticollis**, then **benign infantile epilepsy**, which responded to carbamazepine. It was noticed that the index patient's father had PKD and migraine with aphasia, and his two brothers had hemiplegic migraine with onset in childhood. Further, all 4 family members had the same PRRT2 c.649dupC mutation. Thus, they concluded that heterogeneous paroxysmal disorders were associated with PRRT2 mutations and include paroxysmal torticollis and **hemiplegic migraine**.

Igarashi et al. [17] described a girl with **Down syndrome** who experienced focal seizures and epileptic spasms during infancy. She was diagnosed as having trisomy 21 during the neonatal period, with focal seizures observed at 5 months of age, which were controlled with phenobarbital. However, epileptic spasms appeared at 7 months of age in association with hypsarrhythmia. They performed a mutation analysis of the PRRT2 gene and found a c.841T>C mutation in her, her father, and in her younger brother and thus hypothesized that the focal seizures in the patient were caused by the PRRT2 mutation, whereas the epileptic spasms were attributable to trisomy 21.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have

yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [18] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [19] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [19].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [20]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [21], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank}

Joachims [18] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM^{Rank}_{classify}$ Joachims [18]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [22], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine

ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. PRRT2 related synergies

Note - PRRT2 was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 2^{nd} order combinations of PRRT2 were recorded.

3.1.1. PRRT2 - individual genes

The following genes in combination with PRRT2 showed high rankings - C-C motif chemokine ligand 26 (CCL26), collagen type IX alpha 2 chain (COL9A2), protein disulfide isomerase family A member 5 (PDIA5), FRY microtubule binding protein (FRY), regulating synaptic membrane exocytosis 4 (RIMS4), Kazal type serine peptidase inhibitor domain 1 (KAZALD1), EBF transcription factor 3 (EBF3), contactin associated protein 1 (CNTNAP1), crystallin alpha B (CRYAB), solute carrier family 29 member 1 (Augustine blood group) (SLC29A1), lysyl oxidase like 3 (LOXL3), PHD finger protein 19 (PHF19), C-C motif chemokine receptor 2 (CCR2), palladin, cytoskeletal associated protein (PALLD), microtubule associated protein 1B (MAP1B), solute carrier family 6 member 11 (SLC6A11), protein tyrosine phosphatase non-receptor type 22 (PTPN22), formin homology 2 domain containing 3 (FHOD3), Fraser extracellular matrix complex subunit 1 (FRAS1), aldehyde dehydrogenase 1 family member L1 (ALDH1L1), family with sequence similarity 105, member A (FAM105A), phosphoinositide-3-kinase regulatory subunit 1 (PIK3R1), exostosin glycosyltransferase 1 (EXT1), 15-hydroxyprostaglandin dehydrogenase (HPGD), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 2 (DACT2), microfibril associated protein 4 (MFAP4), transgolgi network vesicle protein 23 homolog A (TVP23A), 5'-nucleotidase domain containing 2 (NT5DC2), filamin A interacting protein 1 like (FILIP1L), RAB31, member RAS oncogene family (RAB31), nephronectin (NPNT), atonal bHLH transcription factor 8 (ATOH8), vesicle associated membrane protein 5 (VAMP5), coiled-coil domain containing 126 (CCDC126), integrin subunit alpha M (ITGAM), microtubule associated protein 6 (MAP6), mono-ADP ribosylhydrolase 2 (MACROD2), interleukin 17D (IL17D), pseudopodium enriched atypical kinase 1 (PEAK1), heart development protein with EGF like domains 1 (HEG1), CD248 molecule (CD248), purinergic recep-

tor P2Y14 (P2RY14), family with sequence similarity 131 member A (FAM131A), calcium binding protein 4 (CABP4), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 3A1 (SLCO3A1), BCL2 family apoptosis regulator BOK (BOK), MEF2 activating motif and SAP domain containing transcriptional regulator (MAMSTR), frizzled class receptor 8 (FZD8), myozenin 1 (MYOZ1), phosphodiesterase 4D interacting protein (PDE4DIP), class II major histocompatibility complex transactivator (CIITA), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 1 (KCNE1), NME/NM23 family member 9 (NME9), PLAG1 zinc finger (PLAG1), exostosin glycosyltransferase 1 (EXT1), biglycan (BGN), EPH receptor B3 (EPHB3), pyrroline-5-carboxylate reductase 1 (PYCR1), nebulin (NEB), family with sequence similarity 43 member B (FAM43B), adrenoceptor alpha 2C (ADRA2C), colony stimulating factor 1 (CSF1), fibronectin leucine rich transmembrane protein 2 (FLRT2), protein kinase cGMP-dependent 1 (PRKG1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily X member 1 (CYP4X1), A-kinase anchoring protein 19 (C2orf88 / AKAP19), kelch repeat and BTB domain containing 12 (KBTBD12), ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase 8 (ENTPD8), serine/threonine kinase 31 (STK31), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 3 (DACT3), adenosine deaminase RNA specific B1 (ADARB1), sialophorin (SPN), chromosome 2 open reading frame 27A (C2orf27A), metallothionein 1F (MT1F), integrin subunit beta like 1 (ITGBL1), delta like canonical Notch ligand 1 (DLL1), dual specificity phosphatase and pro isomerase domain containing 1 (DUSP27), RNA, U6 small nuclear 529, pseudogene (RNU6-529P), synaptotagmin 15 (SYT15), family with sequence similarity 155 member A (FAM155A), transmembrane protein 240 (TMEM240), 3-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydratase 2 (HACD2), RFPL1 antisense RNA 1 (RFPL1S), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 937 (LINC00937), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1907 (LINC01907), ITGB2 antisense RNA 1 (ITGB2-AS1), LMCD1 antisense RNA 1 (LMCD1-AS1) and zinc finger protein 883 (ZNF883).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of PRRT2 with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t PRRT2 with PRRT2 – > CCL26 / COL9A2 / PDIA5 / FRY / RIMS4 / KAZALD1 / EBF3 / CNTNAP1 / CRYAB / SLC29A1 / LOXL3 / PHF19 / CCR2 / PALLD / MAP1B / SLC6A11 / PTPN22 / FHOD3 / FRAS1 / ALDH1L1 / FAM105A / PIK3R1 / EXT1 / HPGD / DACT2 / MFAP4 / TVP23A / NT5DC2 / FILIP1L / RAB31 / NPNT / ATOH8 / VAMP5 / CCDC126 / ITGAM / MAP6 / MACROD2 / IL17D / PEAK1 / HEG1 / CD248 / P2RY14 / FAM131A / CABP4 / SLCO3A1 / BOK / MAMSTR / FZD8 / MYOZ1 / PDE4DIP / CIITA / KCNE1 / NME9 / PLAG1 / EXT1 / BGN / EPHB3 / PYCR1 / NEB / FAM43B / ADRA2C / CSF1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1 / CYP4X1 / C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / ENTPD8 / STK31 / DACT3 / ADARB1 / SPN / C2orf27A / MT1F / ITGBL1 / DLL1 / DUSP27 / RNU6-529P / SYT15 / FAM155A / TMEM240 / HACD2 / RFPL1S / LINC00937 / LINC01907 / ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 / ZNF883.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS PRRT2									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T PRRT2									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
CCL26 - PRRT2	218	2	298	349	COL9A2 - PRRT2	174	323	199	311
PDIA5 - PRRT2	65	210	296	220	FRY - PRRT2	134	212	222	363
RIMS4 - PRRT2	91	245	242	258	KAZALD1 - PRRT2	223	384	85	267
EBF3 - PRRT2	216	226	154	264	CNTNAP1 - PRRT2	55	234	292	231
CRYAB - PRRT2	274	12	280	269	SLC29A1 - PRRT2	283	228	163	312
LOXL3 - PRRT2	257	185	201	226	PHF19 - PRRT2	248	65	207	252
CCR2 - PRRT2	211	242	270	211	PALLD - PRRT2	182	206	215	361
MAP1B - PRRT2	70	240	223	305	SLC6A11 - PRRT2	215	269	178	331
PTPN22 - PRRT2	105	298	229	259	FHOD3 - PRRT2	212	232	25	319
FRAS1 - PRRT2	208	287	128	250	ALDH1L1 - PRRT2	293	11	241	335
FAM105A - PRRT2	47	223	238	286	PIK3R1 - PRRT2	116	263	309	371
EXT1 - PRRT2	330	237	191	221	HPGD - PRRT2	242	268	155	328
DACT2 - PRRT2	175	278	209	242	MFAP4 - PRRT2	246	290	81	262
TVP23A - PRRT2	59	259	263	203	NT5DC2 - PRRT2	367	295	148	235
FILIP1L - PRRT2	344	257	274	194	RAB31 - PRRT2	291	312	182	243
NPNT - PRRT2	342	204	306	255	ATOH8 - PRRT2	302	306	203	139
VAMP5 - PRRT2	382	118	307	337	CCDC126 - PRRT2	331	126	350	232
ITGAM - PRRT2	378	187	317	256	MAP6 - PRRT2	318	133	234	325
MACROD2 - PRRT2	334	165	281	257	IL17D - PRRT2	201	308	329	310
PEAK1 - PRRT2	303	294	213	207	HEG1 - PRRT2	307	372	236	228
CD248 - PRRT2	300	182	310	339	P2RY14 - PRRT2	294	86	358	333
FAM131A - PRRT2	230	386	341	171	CABP4 - PRRT2	326	266	336	314

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between PRRT2 VS Individual members.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS PRRT2									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T PRRT2									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
SLCO3A1 - PRRT2	299	213	382	302	BOK - PRRT2	198	285	288	372
MAMSTR - PRRT2	243	286	331	334	FZD8 - PRRT2	234	376	279	172
MYOZ1 - PRRT2	107	224	312	343	PDE4DIP - PRRT2	197	359	338	246
CIITA - PRRT2	252	265	293	295	KCNE1 - PRRT2	332	293	256	303
NME9 - PRRT2	203	169	284	350	PLAG1 - PRRT2	366	383	259	131
EXT1 - PRRT2	330	237	191	221	BGN - PRRT2	327	324	266	315
EPHB3 - PRRT2	277	253	300	297	PYCR1 - PRRT2	204	319	272	187
NEB - PRRT2	339	104	315	304	FAM43B - PRRT2	244	342	334	355
ADRA2C - PRRT2	178	202	301	374	CSF1 - PRRT2	376	288	359	155
FLRT2 - PRRT2	279	199	384	381	PRKG1 - PRRT2	322	167	289	316
CYP4X1 - PRRT2	364	373	225	145	C2orf88 - PRRT2	273	248	285	240
KBTBD12 - PRRT2	250	247	261	2	ENTPD8 - PRRT2	233	243	373	373
STK31 - PRRT2	224	328	172	251	DACT3 - PRRT2	281	350	268	275
ADARB1 - PRRT2	260	205	320	309	SPN - PRRT2	166	370	349	253
C2orf27A - PRRT2	380	381	161	223	MT1F - PRRT2	120	252	346	324
ITGBL1 - PRRT2	368	281	278	234	DLL1 - PRRT2	147	227	319	326
DUSP27 - PRRT2	329	357	138	229	RNU6-529P - PRRT2	313	272	325	238
SYT15 - PRRT2	254	216	314	360	FAM155A - PRRT2	276	214	363	142
TMEM240 - PRRT2	269	149	324	387	HACD2 - PRRT2	336	375	276	158
RFPL1S - PRRT2	358	339	208	230	LINC00937 - PRRT2	261	221	250	272
LINC01907 - PRRT2	338	161	206	200	ITGB2-AS1 - PRRT2	169	217	380	330
LMCD1-AS1 - PRRT2	251	267	353	383	ZNF883 - PRRT2	361	358	318	208

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between PRRT2 VS Individual members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t PRRT2
CCL26 / COL9A2 / PDIA5 / FRY / RIMS4 ...
KAZALD1 / EBF3 / CNTNAP1 / CRYAB ...
SLC29A1 / LOXL3 / PHF19 / CCR2 / PALLD ...
MAP1B / SLC6A11 / PTPN22 / FHOD3 / FRAS1 ...
ALDH1L1 / FAM105A / PIK3R1 / EXT1 / HPGD ...
DACT2 / MFAP4 / TVP23A / NT5DC2 / FILIP1L ...
RAB31 / NPNT / ATOH8 / VAMP5 / CCDC126 ...
ITGAM / MAP6 / MACROD2 / IL17D / PEAK1 ...
HEG1 / CD248 / P2RY14 / FAM131A / CABP4 ...
SLCO3A1 / BOK / MAMSTR / FZD8 / MYOZ1 ...
PDE4DIP / CIITA / KCNE1 / NME9 / PLAG1 ...
EXT1 / BGN / EPHB3 / PYCR1 / NEB / FAM43B ...
ADRA2C / CSF1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1 / CYP4X1 ...
C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / ENTPD8 / STK31 / DACT3 ...
ADARB1 / SPN / C2orf27A / MT1F / ITGBL1 ...
DLL1 / DUSP27 / RNU6-529P / SYT15 / FAM155A ...
TMEM240 / HACD2 / RFPL1S / LINC00937 ...
LINC01907 / ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 / ZNF883 PRRT2

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between PRRT2 and Individual members.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic PRRT2 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of PRRT2-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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